

THE MAJOR ROLE OF SOCIAL PROBLEMS AND CONSEQUENCE OF INDIAN SOCIETY- CHALLENGES AND SOLUTIONS

Chitrakala N

Associate Professor
of Sociology Government First Grade College, Arasikere, Hassan –District,
Karnataka –State

ABSTRACT

There are also issues that don't fall into either category, such as warfare and it was to be disagreements about what social issues are worth solving, or which should take precedence. Different individuals and different societies have different perceptions for current social issues of major social problems in India include poverty, gender inequality, caste discrimination, unemployment, corruption, and environmental degradation, which limits of social progress and impact millions of lives. Solutions require government initiatives and broad societal participation to promote education, improve healthcare, create job opportunities, and foster a more inclusive and just society through reforms and awareness programs the problems of crime, corruption, law enforcement, environmental degradation, substance abuse, and mental health issues have far-reaching implications for the country's progress. Addressing these problems requires multifaceted strategies involving government, civil society, and community engagement. The caste with joint family system and village communities emerged in the early phase of India society which are also responsible for several of the social problems in the modern period. India has been a multi-religious, metalinguistic, multi-cultural and multi-regional society, since time immemorial. These diversities of Indian society have made significant cultural contributions and certainly they are a source of strength to the rich cultural heritage of India. There are a variety of methods people use to combat social issues of the society change some people all the vote for leaders in a democracy to advance their ideals. Outside the political process, people donate or share their time, money, energy, or other resources. This often takes the form of volunteering. Nonprofit organizations are often formed for the sole purpose of solving a particular social issue. Community organizing involves gathering people together for a common purpose.

Keywords : Social Problems, Society- Challenges and Solutions etc.

INTRODUCTION

It is often the consequence of factors extending beyond an individual's social issue is the source of a conflicting opinion on the grounds of what is perceived as a morally just personal life or societal order. Social issues are distinguished from economic issues; however, some issues (such as immigration) have both social and economic aspects Social Science and Humanities. Social problem is condition in Society which is judged to be undesirable and in need of reform or elimination. The social issues like poverty, unemployment, migration, crime, delinquency, drug abuse, child abuse, crime against women, crime against children, discrimination on the basis of Caste, class & religion , corruption, family and health problems, education, political, economic, cultural and environment issues and human rights violation all need to be seen in the socio economic repercussions. This course explains about the social problems faced by the individuals and the society and introspects how to handle the issues in socioeconomic perspectives. This course is imperative to all Social science and sociology students as it deals with major problems of society and equips them to deal with it to overcome certain issues by helping the concerned individual or society or authorities towards making a better society.

WHAT IS CASTE SYSTEM?

The Indian caste system is based on the cultural features of hierarchy, pollution and purity. It subscribes to the doctrines of Karma and Dharma. The Indian government introduced the category of Scheduled Castes (SCs) to the constitution in 1935. Currently, SCs constitute around 16% of the Indian population. The main issues faced by Dalits are those of untouchability, exploitation, exclusion from religious and educational institutions and social discrimination.

The Indian caste system is a hierarchical, inherited social stratification that has historically assigned individuals to ranked social groups (castes) based on their birth, dictating their occupation, social standing, and marriage prospects.

The caste system is a rigid, birth-determined social hierarchy that assigns individuals to fixed social groups with associated rights and status, often tied to traditional occupations and social customs.

SOCIAL ISSUES AND PROBLEMS

An individual problem is one that affects only a particular individual or group. On the other hand, public issues are those faced by society as a whole. A social issue is when a situation is deemed less than the social ideal. It must result in unfavorable circumstances that can only be handled collectively. These classifications are only the purpose of narration. They are closely interrelated with each other. Poverty is an economic as well as a social problem. Similarly, communalism is closely linked with economic factors and advanced for caste system is a comprehensive, systematized, and institutionalized form of oppression of members of the lower castes, particularly the Dalits. Formalized during the British colonial period, the caste system brings together two related Indian concepts of varna and jāti to create four social orders and multiple subunits. Sitting outside the traditional four orders are the Dalits, who experience social, economic, and religious discrimination due to an inherited status related to traditionally polluting occupations the crime and delinquency are having legal overtones but they are closely related to the social and economic factors. As there were organized social movements against social problems in the previous phases of the Indian society India has undergone many changes in the last decades. Social change brings with it a new set of circumstances wherein an otherwise overlooked issue might be given importance.

AFFIRMATIVE ACTION IN PRACTICE FOR RESERVATION SYSTEM

Affirmative action is implemented as a reservation system, a legal framework that guarantees fixed quotas of spots in government jobs, higher education, and political bodies for historically marginalized communities, including Scheduled Castes (SC), Scheduled Tribes (ST), Other Backward Classes (OBC), and Economically Weaker Sections (EWS). The system aims to provide opportunities for these groups, address past discrimination, and promote social equality by creating a level playing field, though its implementation remains a subject of ongoing debate. Personal issues are those that individuals deal with themselves and within a small range of their peers and relationships. On the other hand, social issues involve values cherished by widespread society. For example, a high unemployment rate that affects millions of people is a social issue. The line between a personal issue and a public issue may be subjective and depends on how groups are defined. However, when a large enough sector of society is affected by an issue, it becomes a social issue. Returning to the unemployment issue, while one person losing their job is a personal and not a social issue, firing 13 million people is likely to generate a variety of social issues the major components of modernization such as education, political participation, urbanization, migration, mobility, money, market, modern technology, communication-network and industrialization were introduced by the colonial administration. They received an impetus in the post-independence period. The independent India

adopted a modern constitution, founded a secular democratic state and followed the policy of planned socio-economic development, democratic decentralization and the policy of protective discrimination for the weaker sections.

A valence issue is a social problem that people uniformly interpret the same way. These types of issues generally generate a widespread consensus and provoke little resistance from the public. An example of a valence issue would be child abuse, which is condemned across several societies to a large enough degree that some social scientists might speak of them as though they are universal, for the sake of illustration. By contrast, a position issue is a social problem in which the popular opinion among society is divided. As a result, in several of the ex-colonial societies – democracy could not function successfully. The ethnic, communal, tribal, caste and regional aspirations have become so strong that they are eroding even the basic structures of democracy, modern state and civic society different people may hold different and strongly-held views, which are not easily changed. An example of a position issue is abortion, which has not generated a widespread consensus from the public, in some countries.

MAJOR SOCIAL PROBLEMS OF INDIAN SOCIETY

The social problems facing India are deeply interlinked with its economic, cultural, and political landscape. Addressing crime, corruption, environmental degradation, and mental health issues requires a comprehensive and integrated approach involving robust policy reforms, public awareness, and active participation from civil society. Civil society plays an instrumental role in tackling social problems by acting as a bridge between the state and the people. Civil society organizations (CSOs), including non-governmental organizations (NGOs), advocacy groups, and grassroots movements, contribute to addressing crime, corruption, environmental issues, and mental health concerns through By addressing these social problems effectively, India can build a more equitable, sustainable, and harmonious society for its diverse population.

CASTE DISCRIMINATION AS GLOBAL ISSUES IN SOCIAL PROBLEMS

While many schools were built, they had poor infrastructure and inadequate facilities. Schools in the rural areas were especially affected. According to District Information System for Education (DISE) in India in 2009, only about 51.5% of all schools in India have boundary walls, 16.65% have computers and 39% have electricity. Of which, only 6.47% of primary schools and 33.4% of upper primary schools have computers, and only 27.7% of primary schools have electricity—Learning in poorly furnished schools was not conducive, resulting in poor quality education.

Furthermore, the absence rates of teachers and students were high, while their detainments rates low. The incentives for going to school were not apparent, while punishment for absence was not enforced. Despite the government's decree on compulsory education and the child labour ban, many children were still missing classes to go to work.

Also, online country studies publications by the Federal Research Division of the Library of Congress stated that “it was not unusual for the teacher to be absent or even to subcontract the teaching work to unqualified substitute this exacerbates the problems of the lack of qualified teachers. Currently, the student-teacher ratio remains high at around 32, which is not much of an improvement since 2006 when the ratio was Economic and social disparities also plague the fundamentals of the education system. Rural children are less able to receive education because of greater opportunity costs, since rural children have to work to contribute to the family's income. According to the Annual Status of Education in 2009, the average attendance rate of students in the rural states is about 75%. Though this rate varies significantly, states like Uttar Pradesh and Bihar had more than 40% absentees during a

random visit to their schools. In the urban states, more than 90% of the students were present in their schools during a visit.

CASTE RELATED VIOLENCE

Over the years, various incidents of violence against Dalits, such as Kherlanji Massacre have been reported from many parts of India. At the same time, many violent protests by Dalits, such as the 2006 Dalit protests in Maharashtra, have been reported as well. The Mandal Commission was established in 1979 to "identify the socially or educationally backward", and to consider the question of seat reservations and quotas for people to redress caste discrimination. In 1980, the commission's report affirmed the affirmative action practice under Indian law whereby members of lower castes were given exclusive access to a certain portion of government jobs and slots in public universities. When V. P. Singh Government tried to implement the recommendations of Mandal Commission in 1989, massive protests were held in the country. Many alleged that the politicians were trying to cash in on caste-based reservations for purely pragmatic electoral purposes. In 1990s, many parties Bahujan Samaj Party (BSP), the Samajwadi Party and the Janata Dal started claiming that they are representing the backward castes. Many such parties, relying primarily on Backward Classes' support, often in alliance with Dalits and Muslims, rose to power in Indian states. At the same time, many Dalit leaders and intellectuals started realizing that the main Dalit oppressors were so called Other Backward Classes, and formed their own parties, such as the Indian Justice Party. The Congress (I) in Maharashtra long relied on OBCs' backing for its political success. Bharatiya Janata Party has also showcased its Dalit and OBC leaders to prove that it is not an upper-caste party. Bangaru Laxman, the former BJP president (2001–2002) was a Dalit. Sanyasin Uma Bharati, former CM of Madhya Pradesh, who belongs to OBC caste, was a former BJP leader. In 2006 Arjun Singh cabinet minister for MHRD of the UPA government was accused of playing caste politics when he introduced reservations for OBCs in educational institutions all around.

CONCLUSION

A small section of the Indian society belongs to the jet age, whereas, a large Indian population even today depend on the bullock-cart. Particularistic tendencies play an important role in the electoral process of the country. India, a diverse and rapidly developing nation, faces a range of social problems that stem from its complex socio-economic structure, rapid urbanization, historical challenges, and disparities in wealth and development. Several political parties have been formed on communal and parochial lines. At the time elections, castes, religion, language and region play significant roles this situation is the clear indicator of the gap between the rich and the poor, the rural and the urban creating a gulf between the different groups.

REFERENCES

1. "Overpopulation in India" (PDF). Serendip.brynmawr.edu. Retrieved 2013-08-24.
2. "Overpopulation in India and China". Web.archive.org. 27 October 2009. Archived from the original on 2009-10-27. Retrieved 17 August 2013.
3. "Over-population warning as India's billionth baby is born". The Guardian. London. 11 May 2000. Retrieved 23 May 2010.
4. "Manas: History and Politics, Indira Gandhi". Sscnet.ucla.edu. Retrieved 17 August 2013.

5. Shawn Donnan (May 9, 2014), World Bank eyes biggest global poverty line increase in decades, The Financial Times
6. "Number and Percentage of Population Below Poverty Line". Reserve Bank of India. 2012. Retrieved 4 April 2014.
7. World Bank's \$1.25/day poverty measure- countering the latest criticisms The World Bank (2010)